
USING TEXTS AND DESIGNING TASKS

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Abstract: Many language textbooks are accompanied by an audio component. Usually, the listening texts are scripted, which means that the spoken discourse was first written out and then read and recorded. Scripted language is an effective teaching tool, but it lacks certain features of authentic input. The speakers speak rather slowly and seldom change the topic of the conversation. Their pronunciation is careful, intonation is exaggerated, sentences are complete, and there is no background noise to distract the listener. This is very different from authentic listening, which involves the language native speakers use in real life. In this article I will show Educators have long been interested in the benefits and drawbacks of using authentic listening materials. On one hand, they allow students to explore the real language and culture and thus increase motivation and interest in learning. On the other hand, coping with the speed, vocabulary, and irregularities of native speech can make authentic listening very difficult, particularly for lower-level students. Moreover, because authentic materials are not accompanied by lesson plans and activities, they require a good deal of preparation on the part of the teacher.

Keywords: *Planning Listening Instruction* for suggestions, formal or informal, *teacher talk*, NNEs, Rost's (2011) framework, Interactive Listening, Extensive Listening, Extensive Listening, Autonomous Listening, cognitive, linguistic, and social skills.

A valuable source of listening (and one rarely recognized as such) is *teacher talk*. As teachers discuss classroom business, answer students' questions, or tell stories, they provide students with natural opportunities for interaction and practicing listening to unscripted speech. This type of input is the easiest to control for difficulty because the teacher can effortlessly paraphrase, repeat, explain, and change the speed of delivery. Keeping the benefits of teacher talk in mind, I try to resist the urge to address my students in their native language to save time when they ask a question about the target culture. I take advantage of their interest in the topic and make my response a listening activity. After announcing a purpose (*I am going to tell you about . . . After listening, you will tell me what you understood*), I tell the story at natural speed and then repeat it more slowly. I consciously monitor my choice of words and use of nonverbal cues, pause to check comprehension, and ask for a summary at the end. Another natural source of aural input is *student talk* that emerges in the individual and group production during class work. Although some students and teachers object to cooperative activities because of the exposure to "poor" language and other speakers' mistakes, use of the native language, and perceived loss of control over the class, the advantages of collaborative work outweigh these concerns. Group activities provide an interactive and safe environment to practice aural and oral skills, maximize listening and speaking time, and enable even the quietest students to participate. Also, many learners find it easier to understand their fellow NNEs. When teachers notice groups of students slipping into their native language, they may remind them that every

minute of the class time should be spent practicing the target language and that learning from each other is very effective because members of the group each have different strengths. To keep students on task, teachers should include relevant information-exchange communicative tasks with a clearly defined role for each participant and set a time limit for each activity.

They should rotate group members to keep activities interesting and walk around the room while correcting oral mistakes, answering questions, and providing individualized feedback on listening and speaking. When students present individually, the rest of the class should be told to listen and ask questions, summarize, or report back.

Reading and writing skills are part of the work of scientists, and hence also need to be part of the science curriculum (Bradbury, [Citation2014](#); Cervetti et al., [Citation2012](#)). The field of science has its own academic language: vocabulary, as well as specific discourse patterns not present in students' everyday language, but needed for learning (Huerta & Garza, [Citation2019](#)). Second, working with authentic language activities is very important for promoting language proficiency (Purcell-Gates et al., [Citation2007](#)). Inquiry-based learning within science education offers many opportunities for such authentic language tasks, for example aimed at acquiring knowledge. Being engaged in knowledge building while reading a text increases interest and intrinsic motivation for reading, and thereby promotes deeper text processing (Jetton & Alexander, [Citation2001](#); Wang & Guthrie, [Citation2004](#)). In addition, hands-on investigation offers many possibilities for authentic writing tasks, such as logs and reports (Cervetti et al., [Citation2009](#)).

Design principles

The purpose of our DBR was to develop science-and-literacy-integrated teaching materials with a focus on text structure instruction and, since the study took

place in the context of Dutch primary education, aimed at language proficiency of Dutch. In terms of the integration staircase, which orders different types of integration in terms of complexity (Gresnigt et al., [Citation2014](#)), the approach in our study can be characterized as interdisciplinary integration. At this level of integration, two or more school subjects are organized around the same theme or topic, but the disciplines preserve their identity. Based on insights from previous research on reading comprehension and integrated programs, we formulated four design principles (DPs), which we will explain in the next paragraphs.

Selecting concepts

DP1. Select concepts that enable hands-on activities and evoke understanding processes and/or understanding causal relationships and/or comparing and classifying content.

Instruction about text structures such as the ones in Table 1 seems compatible with the three-dimensional learning described in the Framework for K-12 Science Education (National Research Council, [Citation2012](#)). This entails understanding of *core conceptual ideas* occurs through engagement in *science activities* and by using *crosscutting concepts* as lenses or bridges that can support students' science sensemaking (Fick et al., [Citation2022](#); Rivet et al., [Citation2016](#)). The connection aimed at in DP1 is supposed to work two ways. First, during science activities students can observe sequential processes, compare objects or phenomena, or predict the effects of certain operations, and experience the characteristics of these coherence relations at first hand (Cervetti et al., [Citation2006](#)). Second, learning to recognize the structure of texts within the context of science education can support students' conceptual understanding (Montelongo et al., [Citation2010](#)) and thereby facilitate the use of the crosscutting concepts (Fick et al., [Citation2022](#)).

Hands-on activities

DP2. Organize hands-on activities that facilitate the comprehension of the concept and its context.

Experiencing science concepts through hands-on activities is motivating and promotes active thinking and discourse around activities. Several scientists agree that science and literacy share a set of meaning making strategies and are thus synergistically related (Cervetti et al., [Citation2006](#); Guthrie et al., [Citation1999](#); Stoddart et al., [Citation2002](#)). Working on these strategies in both inquiry and literacy activities can reinforce conceptual understanding as well as language proficiency (Bradbury, [Citation2014](#); Huntley, [Citation1998](#); Pratt & Pratt, [Citation2004](#)). Extending this premise to text structure instruction, it is important to not only familiarize students with coherence relations such as sequence, or cause-effect during reading lessons, but also let them perceive and explicate such relations in real-world experiences.

Intensive Listening

Intensive listening means paying close attention to the language of the listening text to single out words or phrases, grammatical structures, specific sounds, or intonation patterns.

Selective Listening

Selective listening involves concentrating on specific details with a deliberate purpose in mind. It is usually done to extract information in response to a particular task, such as *Listen and say when the train leaves* or *Write down the telephone number*. Whereas intensive listening focuses on the precise language of the message, selective listening attends to essential bits of the content, disregarding irrelevant information. To engage in selective listening, students could practice.

Interactive**Listening**

Interactive listening requires the listener to participate in the conversation by alternating between listening and speaking. This back-and-forth interaction involves not only listening but also producing the language: negotiating the meaning, confirming understanding, taking turns, and delivering an appropriate response. It is the ultimate form of aural and oral practice that integrates linguistic forms, meaning, and social conventions of listening.

Extensive Listening

Extensive listening focuses on general comprehension of the text. It means getting the overall meaning and enjoying the content rather than seeking answers to specific questions. It exposes students to different voices and styles, improves automaticity in processing spoken language, and builds confidence in dealing with the spoken input. The following activities are based on extensive listening:

- > summarizing
- > rating content as more or less interesting using visual organizers
- > filling out listening logs, in which students record their listening goals and strategies for each text
- > practicing good listening, in which students listen to several recordings on self-selected topics

Responsive Listening

Responsive listening makes the listener relate to the content of the text by expressing an opinion, a feeling, or a point of view. Rather than appealing to facts, it elicits personal attitudes and emotions. This type of response may be colored by one's sociocultural background because the same content could cause different reactions from different cultures.

Autonomous**Listening**

Autonomous listening describes any independent listening that is done outside the classroom. It promotes learner motivation and self-reliance because the choice of materials, comprehension monitoring, and task completion are determined by the listener. To help students cope with listening on their own, teachers can provide training in strategies and self-assessment techniques. Autonomous listening includes all the types of listening described in this “Listening Activities” section.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, text-based instruction can be a useful approach for teaching a foreign language to future pedagogues. However, it is important to consider the advantages and disadvantages of this approach and to balance it with other methods that emphasize interactive, communicative, and cultural aspects of language learning. By combining various methods, teachers can provide a more comprehensive and effective language learning experience for their students.

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